

Mucinous Neoplasm of Appendix: Treatment

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Abstract:-

AIM: This study aims to treatment for mucinous neoplasm of appendix

MATERIAL AND METHODS: A prospective descriptive study was done in patient with history of pain abdomen and distension presented to our hospital

RESULTS: We provide an overview of the most recent information and conflicts about the classification of AMNs, clinical manifestations, and the effectiveness of cytoreductive surgery and hyperthermic intraperitoneal chemotherapy (HIPEC)

CONCLUSION: Appendiceal mucinous tumors are frequently an incidental finding. The treatment of this disease depends on the Histologic tumor grade and the presence of peritoneal dissemination will determine surgery which includes, from appendectomy to cytoreductive surgery. The treatment for Low-grade tumors includes resection of the primary site in early stage disease, or peritoneal debulking and for advance stage includes HIPEC. While treatment for high-grade tumors include debulking surgery and HIPEC with or without preoperative chemotherapy.

Keywords:- Mucinous Neoplasms of Appendix, Appendix, Treatment.

I. INTRODUCTION

These are the rare tumors accounting for less than 1% of all cancers. The way the symptoms manifest themselves can vary, but the most common symptoms is right iliac fossa abdominal pain, which can be misdiagnosed as acute appendicitis. Low grade tumors that are limited to the appendix are typically benign. On the other hand, tumors that have invaded the appendiceal wall or have a high degree of atypia may grow rapidly and are classified as adenocarcinomas.

Types of Mucinous appendiceal tumors are 1) mucinous cystadenoma (MC), 2) mucinous tumors of uncertain malignant potential (M-UMP), 3) mucinous tumors with low malignant potential (M-LMP) and 4) mucinous adenocarcinoma (MA). The treatment of AMN is largely based on stage and histology.

II. CASE SERIES

A. Case 1

A elderly obese female (BMI – 30.6 kg/m²) presented to the out-patient of surgery department in tertiary care center in July 2021, with a pain abdomen since 6 months with no history of chronic cough/ tuberculosis as well as in close contacts. On examination patient compliant of right iliac fossa pain with rest of the physical examination being normal. Ultrasonography of abdomen and pelvis was performed which suggested sealed off appendicular perforation. The patient was planned for an explorative laprotomy. Intra-operatively a appendix was enlarged and perforation was seen at the tip of the appendix and appendectomy was performed and specimen was sent for HPE and the wound was closed with primary interrupted sutures. HPE report suggested of low grade mucinous carcinoma of appendix. The scar healed by primary intension and the patient was followed up for a duration of 3 months having no recurrence.

B. Case 2

A elderly male (BMI – 28.9 kg/m²) presented to the out-patient of surgery department in tertiary care center in December 2021, with abdominal distension and pain abdomen since 3 months. Patient has no history of chronic cough/ tuberculosis as well as in close contacts. On examination patient Local guarding was seen in right iliac fossa with minimal ascitis fluid with bowel sound present. Ultrasonography of abdomen was performed which suggested Appendicular perforation with minimal ascitis and CECT Abdomen was done which showed appendicular perforation with periappendicular collection with ascitis with no lymphnode enlargement. The patient was planned for an explorative laprotomy. Intra-operatively appendicular perforation was seen at the tip with mucin deposition in the abdomen and appendectomy was done and specimen was sent for HPE and the wound was closed with primary interrupted sutures. HPE report suggested of low grade mucinous carcinoma of appendix. The scar healed by primary intension with no recurrence during the follow up period of 2 months.

C. Case 3

An elderly male presented to the out-patient of surgery department in tertiary care centre in May 2022 with a pain abdomen since 6 months and abdominal distension and pain abdomen since 3 months. Physical examination patient Local guarding was seen in right iliac fossa with minimal ascitic fluid with bowel sound present. The rest of the physical examination was under normal limits with no other swelling/lump noted in the axilla, groin or the neck. Ultrasonography of abdomen was performed which suggested Appendicular perforation with minimal ascitis and CECT Abdomen was done which showed appendicular perforation with periappendicular collection with ascitis with no lymphnode enlargement. Patient was planned for surgery – Explorative Laparotomy. Intra-operatively appendicular perforation was seen at the tip with mucin deposition in the abdomen and appendectomy was done excised specimen was sent for HPE and the wound was closed with primary interrupted sutures. HPE report suggested low grade mucinous carcinoma of appendix. The scar healed by primary intension with no recurrence during the follow up period of 6 months.

III. DISCUSSION

Appendiceal mucinous neoplasms account for 0.4%–1% of all gastrointestinal malignancies, According to estimates, there are 0.12 cases of AMN per 1 million people each year. The majority of appendiceal tumor patients (70–74%) are white, and 50%–55% of them are women. Over time, no discernable demographic change has been seen.

The most frequent clinical manifestation in early stage disease is right lower abdomen pain, which the patient may experience as a result of the appendix being distended by mucus. If the tumor blocks the appendiceal orifice and ruptures, there may be appendiceal perforation.

The buildup of mucous ascites in the peritoneum causes abdominal distension in advanced stages of the disease. Chronic stomach pain, weight loss, anemia, infertility, and newly developed umbilical or inguinal hernias are additional clinical manifestations for this stage.

Ronnett's classification system was then updated and simplified into low- and high-grade carcinoma, where any mucinous epithelium beyond the muscularis mucosa is unambiguous evidence of an invasive appendiceal malignancy. Peritoneal mucinous carcinomatosis (PMCA) and disseminated peritoneal adenomucinosis (DPAM) were further divided into three forms by Bradley et al.

- well-differentiated mucinous adenocarcinoma, grade 1 of (DPAM),
- mucinous adenocarcinoma, grade 2 of 3 (PMCA-I type),
- high-grade mucinous adenocarcinoma, grade 3 of 3 (PMCA type).

➤ Localized AMNs

The majority of surgical research implies that a straightforward appendectomy is sufficient for tumors demonstrating only local malignancy since the incidence of nodal spread of well-differentiated localized appendiceal malignancies is less than 2%. In case of positive margins after appendectomy, Right hemicolectomy should be considered as the next step of management. The same is to be considered for peri-appendiceal tumors. Tumor size of 2 cm or larger, high grade histology, or tumor that invades through the muscularis propria, criteria for right hemicolectomy include the following: (1) degree of cellular undifferentiation, (2) increased mitotic activity, (3) Appendicular base involvement (4) metastasis to lymph nodes, or (e) tumor size more than 2 cm. As mentioned above features are risk factor for local recurrences, thus supporting right hemicolectomy.

➤ Treatment of AMN with Peritoneal Metastasis

In these patient main stay of treatment includes repeated drainage of the mucinous ascites and serial debulking surgeries. They were also study which showed intraperitoneal chemotherapy with debulking surgery improved the condition of the patient.

IV. CONCLUSION

Staging and histology type are needed for treatment. The treatment for Low-grade tumors includes resection of the primary site in early stage disease, or peritoneal debulking and for advance stage includes HIPEC. Treatment of high-grade tumors options include debulking surgery and HIPEC, with or without preoperative chemotherapy.

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